

[View this email in your browser](#)

CHAMPION Project Newsletter

Issue 7, May 2024

CHAMPION Project coming to a close

Welcome to the final edition of the CHAMPION newsletter. After nearly four years of challenging work, we share some of our final project achievements. As in most projects, CHAMPION goes out with a bang, with many final activity reports submitted in the last months and a successful final event. We thank all readers for your interest in our project and hope that some of its successes may inspire your activities to help transition to a bio-based economy.

CHAMPION candidate selection process

The selection process of CHAMPION lead candidates has been a challenging process. Computational modelling and preliminary property screening reduced the more than 500 possible candidates to 180, of which 69 candidates progressed to initial performance testing by end-users. Alongside, toxicity screening, initial techno-economic evaluation, life-cycle analysis and end-of-life assessments were completed for selected promising candidates. This resulted in four lead candidates remaining, of which three went through advanced testing by end-users, seeking to demonstrate high performance in an industrially relevant setting.

Details on the approach and results of each of these steps have been included in a series of reports,

research. In addition, reports were produced on safety tests in a context of polymer application, on recovery and chemical recycling of the lead candidates, and on further steps for formal registration and ongoing full safety evaluation of the selected candidates.

Analysis of overarching sustainability of CHAMPION products

An important requirement in the CHAMPION project is to ensure that the novel bio-based polymers target safety and circularity by design. In other words, that they are safe, have lower health risks than their fossil alternatives and that (chemical) recyclability or biodegradability are possible. To this end, the potential applications have been tested by the project industry end-users and their environmental performance was guided by extensive life-cycle assessment (LCA) using the EN 16751 standard, which served as the core framework for evaluation.

The results show a positive evaluation with regards to climate protection, that the selected polymers can be safe by design, and that they can be produced from primary crops that are grown, harvested, or produced in the EU with reliable supply logistics and known or predictable prices. In terms of circularity, the project has suggested bio-based routes and products with a high renewable carbon content and has identified practices and actions to increase circularity in the upstream and core stages of production. However, further research is needed to achieve full circularity at the end-of-life.

Market and regulatory assessment

based polymers were selected in the CHAMPION project and assessed for toxicity, biodegradability, recyclability, life-cycle performance, environmental performance, and end-user applicability. Following these assessments, a market and regulatory assessment was conducted for each of these selected polymers and their specific applications. One of the main overall conclusions is that the risks related to

feedstock availability and economics for these CHAMPION polymers are considered minimal. As the case for sugar is more specific, the report identifies the impacts of societal and regulatory changes and identifies options for how to address this.

While new bio-based products are becoming increasingly available to replace conventional fossil-based products, a gap in production scale and therewith costs still exists. The report identifies some of the barriers and the expected developments that support closing this gap, including regulatory developments and sustainability certification.

Dissemination and exploitation

While the focus of the CHAMPION project was on the selection and testing of the lead candidates for specific applications, the project has resulted in many more lessons learned, which partners plan to use in further work. A total of 31 results have been identified for further exploitation. For each of these results, an exploitation plan was drafted, focusing on the protection and exploitation of each result and providing an expected timeline for exploitation.

Another project ambition was to reach a wider audience to be informed about the possibilities of bio-based products and the transition to a circular economy. To that extent, various dissemination materials were developed, such as webinars, quizzes, a comic book (more information later in this newsletter) a green chemistry tool for reaction optimisation, and various learning materials for primary school and high-school children. An overview of these dissemination materials is available on the [CHAMPION learning webpage](#).

Final Project Stakeholder Event

Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications

24 April 2024, 09:00–17:00 CET

**BIP Meeting Center,
Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels**

Free Registration • In-person Event

These projects receive funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887398 and No 101022370. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

On 24 April 2024, the CHAMPION team organised the stakeholder event 'Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications' in Brussels. The event was organised in close cooperation with the PERFE COAT project, with a range of speakers from both projects as well as from sibling projects HARMONITOR, 3-Co and LIGNICOAT. In addition, three presentations were provided by the European Commission, including from the CHAMPION project officer and two experts from DG GROW. The event was sold out, and the more than 110 participants actively engaged in Q&A sessions, visited the poster exhibitions, looked at the display of innovations developed in the two projects and used the several networking opportunities to exchange with their peers.

Green Kid comic book

At the final event, the Green Kid comic book was launched, which was developed in the CHAMPION project. The comic book tells the story of fully sustainable wind turbines that have been developed with the CHAMPION system. These turbines are made entirely from bio-based or recycled products, produced using only renewable energy, use non-toxic components that safely degrade at the end of life, and feature adhesives that switch off at the molecular level, allowing the materials to be reused. These innovative wind turbines are, however, sabotaged by a famous criminal. But the Green Kid comes to the rescue to show that click chemistry used in producing the blades of the wind turbine allows for the re-use of the components and a successful operation of the wind turbines.

In addition to the lead story, the comic book also includes some explanations of the circular economy, the science behind developing the CHAMPION polymers, a glossary of key terminology and some puzzles. The comic book is being distributed to scholars in several countries where CHAMPION partners are based, so far in the Netherlands, Portugal and the United Kingdom.

Partners

- [University of York](#)
- [Wageningen Food & Biobased Research \(WFBR\)](#)
- [BioDetection Systems BV](#)
- [Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy](#)
- [Process Design Center BV](#)
- [OWS NV](#)
- [Circa Sustainable Chemicals Ltd](#)
- [Unilever UK Central Resources Ltd](#)
- [nova-Institut für Politische und Ökologische Innovation GmbH](#)
- [Ava Biochem BSL AG](#)
- [Stahl International BV](#)
- [Orineo BV](#)
- [SQ Consult BV](#)
- [Scott Bader Co Ltd](#)

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887398. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio Based Industries Consortium.

Want to change how you receive these emails?
You can [update your preferences](#) or [unsubscribe from this list](#).

